

Building A Metacognition Skills Scale For The Curricula Of The Departments Of Quranic Sciences And Islamic Education In Iraqi Universities

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 27, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 30, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Building, Quranic Sciences, Islamic Education, Faculties Of Education</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6189907</p>	<p><i>The problem of the current research arises in an attempt to reveal the extent to which the teaching of forensic sciences in the faculties of education practice metacognitive skills, as it is not possible to identify the degree of their use without measuring them, and because the processes of measuring and revealing skills make it easier for officials to develop appropriate plans and take appropriate decisions. Measuring metacognitive skills requires the availability of a standardized scale for them, to test the extent to which teachers practice these skills, and the world today is witnessing a rapid movement of development that has made the individual in dire need to adapt to it, and the objectives of the curriculum emphasized the need to provide the opportunity for each learner to develop his abilities to the fullest extent. Modern trends have called for the need to include meta-knowledge skills in all curriculum activities, as it has become necessary to teach students how to think, not how to memorize the capabilities of the curriculum without understanding, assimilating and applying them in life. It fits the current era.</i></p>

Introduction

The importance of the current research stems from the importance of:

1. Education, which bears the responsibility of educating the individual and developing him in all aspects, mental, physical, psychological, social and spiritual so that one aspect does not dominate over another, and aims to prepare the righteous individuals in a comprehensive and integrated manner to be of benefit to themselves and their society. The basis of reform and peasant
2. Faculties of Education, because they are the pivotal link in universities, because of their deep connection with both the university and society, as they work on preparing future teachers, developing scientific research, and preparing researchers, which by its weakness and incapacity and marginalization and confusion of its role leads to confusion and incapacitation of society
3. Forensic sciences as they occupy an important space within the knowledge that people need to straighten their lives.
4. Department of Quran Sciences, which is the best department to provide students with knowledge and Islamic sciences.
5. Metacognitive skills that improve what the individual learns, make him capable of self-learning, increase his confidence and make him able to attribute his success to himself.
6. Teaching methods as they work to achieve the educational goals required in the various stages of study.
7. The teacher who plays an important role in teaching metacognitive skills.

Third: Research objectives

The current research aims to build a measure of metacognitive skills for the curricula of the departments of Quranic sciences and Islamic education in Iraqi universities

Fourth: Research Limits

1. The objective limit: is to know the extent to which teachers of Islamic sciences in the faculties of education practice metacognitive skills
2. The human limit: It is represented by the teachers of Sharia sciences in the faculties of education
3. Spatial Limit: Colleges of Education in Baghdad University of Baghdad, Al-Mustansiriya, Iraq
4. Time limit: the academic year 2020-2021 AD.

Fifth: Defining the terms

Scale - :It is a set of stimuli arranged in order to measure some mental processes or psychological traits or characteristics(Al-Obaidi, 2011: 116)

Metacognition skills

They are those skills that make the individual able to control his thinking, and be aware of his cognitive processes and products.

Department of Quranic Sciences and Islamic Education

It is an academic scientific department within the faculties of education, in which students receive the sciences of the Qur'an and its supporting sciences, in addition to other educational sciences (Al-Dulaimi, 2018: 13)

Chapter Two: Theoretical Background

Metacognition skills

These are processes of control and direction known as metacognitive skills, and they are considered among the complex mental skills and are one of the most prominent components of intelligent behavior in information processing, as they grow with age on the one hand, and as a result of the various and long experiences that the individual goes through on the other hand, as it performs a task Controlling all activities directed to solving various problems, in addition to that, it means that the individual becomes more aware of his actions and their impact on others, and it has an important role in managing time and effort in carrying out difficult tasks, as this includes understanding the problem before rushing to try to solve it and also includes planning, follow-up and control Estimating the type of work and the way it is carried out, and the time that may take to perform this work, and that the ultimate goal of metacognition skills is to teach students to think skillfully by training them to think independently, and to confront themselves, away from teaching indoctrination as much as possible.

Afaneh and Khazindar (2009) model of metacognitive skills

Afaneh and Al-KhazNadar believes that metacognition seeks to educate the learner about the patterns of thinking he uses in light of his awareness of the methods of controlling, controlling and controlling the learning processes, or organizing those processes in order to assimilate and understand the contents of learning .From this standpoint, metacognition is divided into two main components:

A - Self-awareness of knowledge.

B- Self-regulation of knowledge.

The first component: self-awareness of knowledge: This component includes three main types of knowledge identified by (Afaneh, Al-KhazNadar, 2009: 127) as follows:

1-Conceptual knowledge: This knowledge includes several types of knowledge, which are as follows:

1. Awareness of concepts: This means the learner's knowledge of the concepts that he deals with, his awareness of their components and the relationship of those concepts among them.
2. NS Terminology awareness: the awareness of the meaning of scientific, mathematical, social or economic terms.
3. NSSymbol awareness: It is an understanding and awareness of the meaning of abstract symbols, and what they mean if they come within a certain content, and whether these symbols are meaningful or not.
4. NSAwareness of the laws: This means knowing the components of the law, whether it is in the sciences, a positive administrative law, a constitutional law, or others, and knowing the relationship of this law with other relevant laws.

2-Procedural knowledge: This knowledge includes different types of knowledge, which are as follows:

1. Awareness of steps: meaning the learner's knowledge of the steps he may follow in reaching the goal or in solving a mathematical problem, without addressing the solution or implementing the plan to reach the goal, but rather in knowing the action of a specific thing and not its implementation.
2. Knowing models: that is, being aware of certain types of shapes or schemes that are related to a specific content, through awareness of the steps of their formation or organization.
3. Knowing solutions: This knowledge refers to the ways to solve a specific issue or problem, whether it is an issue in science or a specific social problem, where the learner can understand the steps of the solution or the method of dealing with the problem.
4. Knowledge of structures: This means the learner's awareness of how to construct a specific sentence, draw a specific model, build a specific plan, or install a computer, i.e. awareness of the steps of construction and installation.

3-Contextual knowledge: This knowledge includes the following:

1. Awareness of conditions: that is, realizing the conditions for learning a specific problem, or giving conditions for the occurrence of a certain learning or behavior, as this behavior and this situation cannot occur if there are no certain conditions or conditions for its occurrence.
2. B - Perceive reasons: the learner cannot understand a specific situation unless he realizes specific reasons for the existence of something.
3. Giving justifications: This means to provide justifications for the occurrence of a particular phenomenon, and to clarify the weaknesses in that phenomenon or situation, that is, to clarify why the learner was unable to solve the issue.
4. Defining standards: that is, setting standards or units of measurement. For example, in order for a reaction to occur, standards must be available in the reaction materials in order for this reaction to occur.

5. Y- Problem solving: meaning understanding the issue or problem, whether it is typical or atypical, and trying to solve it using a specific strategy.

The second component: the self-organization of knowledge: This component includes three types of knowledge as defined by (Afaneh and Al-KhazNadar, 2009: 130-129), as follows:

1-Knowledge management: It includes the following:

1. Defining strategies: selecting and planning a specific strategy of value and benefit for knowledge management.
2. NS Developing plans: where knowledge management requires the development of plans to implement a specific cognitive task.
3. NSBuilding steps: This level requires the formation of a set of arranged steps to accomplish a particular task.
4. NS Awareness of relationships: This means understanding the relationships that exist between the different aspects of the cognitive situation. A learner cannot be aware of the cognitive contents without being aware of the sequence of those contents and the relationships between their concepts and components.
5. NS Creating conditions: In order for the task to be accomplished and mastered, the appropriate conditions or classroom environment must be created to achieve that task.

2-Knowledge assessment: This knowledge includes the following:

1. Pattern modification: This means that the learner adjusts his learning pattern or the patterns of behavior he uses and attempts to change this pattern in the light of convincing justifications.
2. B - Switching a strategy: The learner may see that the strategy he used to achieve the goals was not useful in developing his abilities and in improving his skills towards a specific task or specific situation, so the learner resorts to modifying that strategy with a more useful one.
3. NS -Improving the context: After the learner uses a certain method to present his ideas in a specific style, and finds that this method was not convincing or expressive, he resorts to reformulating the context in a better way using a certain method in presenting the intellectual contents to improve the context of the topic to become attractive or convincing.
4. x -Verification of the solution: It is a method used by the learner to verify the validity of a certain topic or idea or a special hypothesis, in order to give confidence in the steps he used.

3-Organizing knowledge: This type of knowledge includes the following:

1. Re-planning: In light of revealing the strengths and weaknesses so that the learner can reorganize the scheme or the steps he uses in teaching or thinking, after he puts his hand on the mistakes of not reaching the required goals.
2. NS Modifying outcomes: the teacher can modify specific outcomes through the feedback available in the classroom environment or by modifying himself.
3. NS Clarifying errors: This means clarifying errors and how they occur ?Where does it happen ?And when does it occur ?In order to fade and get rid of them in his thinking or in the learning methods he uses.
4. NSMaking treatments: This means making immediate treatments for learning steps or for thinking patterns used in solving a scientific issue, for example, and this is done through follow-up and review.
5. NS -Organizing thinking: This level is the highest level of metacognition, which means that the learner organizes his thinking from time to time in a comprehensive manner, according to the circumstances and conditions he is going through). Afaneh and KhazNadar 2009: 131-132)

The researchers adopted the model of Afaneh and Al-Khaznadar (2009) for metacognitive skills for the following justifications:

1. The suitability of this model to achieve the objectives of the current research, as it is an objective model that divides metacognition skills into two main components. The first is concerned with self-awareness of knowledge and ensures three main types of knowledge, and the second is self-organization of knowledge and includes three types of knowledge.
2. NSThis model differs from other models that aim to measure metacognitive skills in that the latter relied on measuring only one component, while this model relied on metacognitive skills comprehensively.
3. NS There is no local or Arab study that dealt with the Afana and Al-Khaznadar model of metacognitive skills in the first two components, self-awareness of knowledge, and the second, self-regulation of knowledge, to the knowledge of the two researchers.

Chapter Three: Study methodology and procedures

First: Research Methodology

The researchers adopted the descriptive research method, because it is compatible with the nature and objective of the study, as it is a general study of a phenomenon that exists in a group, in a specific place and at the present time. The problem of research and interpretation of the results, and finally to reach conclusions (Darwish, 2018: 118)

Second: The research community

The study population consisted of (100) male and female teachers, with (52) teachers distributed over the departments of Holy Quran and Islamic Education in government universities in Baghdad governorate, with (7) teachers at the University of Baghdad, the College of Education, Ibn Al-Rushd, and (4) teachers at the University of Baghdad, the College of Education. For girls, (9) male teachers at Al-Mustansiriya University, College of Education, (17) female teachers at the Iraqi University, College of Education, and (15) female teachers at the Iraqi University, College of Education for Girls. The Noble Qur'an and Islamic Education in public universities in the province of Baghdad, with (7) female teachers at the University of Baghdad, the Ibn Al-Rushd College of Education, (18) female teachers at the University of Baghdad, the College of Education for Girls, (10) female teachers at Al-Mustansiriya University, the College of Education, and (2) Female teachers at the Iraqi University, the College of Education, and (11) female teachers at the Iraqi University, the College of Education for Girls. Table (3) shows this:

Table (3) Research community distributed by university, college, and gender

Total		Instructions		teachers		the college	the University
percentage	the number	percentage	the number	percentage	the number		
% 14	14	% 7	7	7%	7	Education - IbnRushd	Baghdad
% 22	22	%18	18	%4	4	Education for girls	
% 19	19	%10	10	%9	9	Education	Al-Mustansiriya
% 19	19	% 2	2	17%	17	Education	Iraqi
% 26	26	11%	11	%15th	15th	Education for girls	
100%	100	48%	48	52%	52	Total	

Third: The study sample

The method of determining the sample size varies according to the specific objectives of the research, the level of accuracy or control, the level of confidence and the method of selecting the sample used is the random sample method. The researchers adopted two methods

To determine the sample size

1-Table (Krejcie& Morgan)

It is a table that determines the percentage of the sample from the original population based on some criteria such as the research method, and the size of the community, as it shows the required sample size with a confidence level (0.95) and an error rate (0.05) Appendix (2)

2-Sample Size Calculator

The sample size calculator is a software that provides a public service to determine the sample size) Sample Size Calculator)Through one of the sites that provides the service of obtaining and accurately obtaining the required number of individuals compared to the community, and it requires filling the void in two sites first(confidence interval (which means (degree of confidence) and the second) Margin of Error (i.e)error percentage) or (significance level), which is determined or accepted by the researcher .In order to find out the required sample size for a population of size (100), indicate or specify the level of confidence, the percentage of error, and the size of the population, then ask for the sample size through the instruction)Sample Size Calculator (So the required number is (81), which matches the number extracted from equations and tables ,as shown in Figure (3) Figure (3)Sample size calculation application interface

Find Out the Margin of Error

This calculator gives out the margin of error or confidence interval of an observation or survey.

Result

Margin of error: **0.00%**

This means, in this case, there is a 95% chance that the real value is within $\pm 0.00\%$ of the measured/surveyed value.

Confidence Level:
 Sample Size:
 Population Proportion:
 Population Size: Leave blank if unlimited population size.

Accordingly, the researchers randomly selected a sample of (81) teachers in the original research community of (100), distributed by (42) teachers to the affiliated colleges of government universities in the province of Baghdad, and (6) teachers at the University of Baghdad, College of Education Ibn Al-Rushd, And (3) a teacher at the University of Baghdad, College of Education for Girls, (7) a teacher at Al-Mustansiriya University, the College of Education, (14) a teacher at the Iraqi University, College of Education, and (12) a teacher at the Iraqi University, College of Education for Girls. (39) female teachers, distributed among the colleges affiliated with government universities in the governorate of Baghdad, with (6) female teachers at the University of Baghdad, the College of Education, Ibn Al-Rushd, (14) female teachers at the University of Baghdad, the College of Education for Girls, and (8) female teachers at Al-Mustansiriya University, the College of Education. And (2) a female teacher at the Iraqi University, the College of Education, and (9) a female teacher at the Iraqi University, the College of Education for Girls, and that the sample size represents (81%) of the size of the community. Table (4) shows the sample size by university, college and gender.

Table (4) the research sample of Islamic education teachers distributed by university, college and gender

Total		Instructions		Teachers		the college	the University
percentage	the number	percentage	the number	percentage	the number		
% 14	12	% 7	6	7%	6	Education - IbnRushd	Baghdad
% 22	17	%18	14	%4	3	Education for girls	
% 19	15 th	%10	8	%9	7	Education	Al-Mustansiriya
% 19	16	% 2	2	17%	14	Education	Iraqi
% 26	21	11%	9	%15th	12	Education for girls	
100%	81	48%	39	52%	42	Total	

Fourth: Measure building procedures:

The procedures for building any scale include basic steps, and the following is a presentation of the steps that followed the construction of the current scale:

1. Define the concept to be measured :In order for the researchers to be able to rely on the concept in preparing the test, the researchers adopted the Afana and Khazindar model (for metacognitive skills)
2. Identify the basic components of the tool The researchers adopted the model of Afana and Al-Khaznadar for metacognition skills in determining the components of the research scale, as it was classified into two components:

The first component: self-awareness of knowledge

The second component: the self-regulation of knowledge

Under each component there are several types of main knowledge, counting them (3) types for each component of metacognitive skills, so that the total number of the main skills of metacognition for the components (6) skills under which (27) sub-skills constitute their sub-components, and the table (3) shows that

Table 3the main skills and sub-skills of the Metacognitive Skills Scale in its initial form

Sub skills	main skills	basic ingredients
A- Awareness of concepts	First - Conceptual knowledge:	The first component: self-awareness of knowledge
B- Awareness of terminology		
C- awareness of the symbol		
D- Awareness of the laws		
E- Realizing the steps	Second - procedural knowledge:	
F- Knowledge of models		
G- Knowing solutions		
H- Knowing the structures		
I- Awareness of conditions	Third - contextual knowledge:	
J- Realizing the reasons		
K- Give justifications		
L- Setting standards		
M- Problem solving		
N- Define strategies	Fourth - knowledge management:	The second component: the self-regulation of knowledge
Q- Make plans		
P- Building steps		
P- Awareness of relationships		

R- Creating conditions	Fifthly, knowledge assessment:	
S- Modify style		
T- Switch strategy		
U- Improving context		
C- Make sure of the solution		
W- Re-scheme	Sixth, organizing knowledge:	
G- Modify outputs		
Y- Clarify errors		
Z- work processors		
G- Organizing thinking		
27	6	

These components were presented to a group of experts specialized in curricula, teaching methods, psychology, measurement and evaluation, and their number reached (17) experts, and (41) paragraphs of supplement (7) were deleted, with (25) paragraphs modified by the experts, and (106) were kept. Annex paragraph (8), and it relied on a criterion (%) or more as the percentage of agreement in keeping, deleting or modifying the paragraphs. Accordingly, the paragraphs that obtained the percentage of experts' agreement (%) were kept at the level of significance (0.05) using the chi-square for one sample, and the paragraphs that obtained the percentage of experts' agreement (%) were kept at the level of significance (0.05) by using the chi-square for one sample, and it was promised Each paragraph is valid when the calculated chi-square value is a function at the level (0.05)

3- Determine the degree of importance of each area of the scale:

Accordingly, the researchers determined the relative weight of each field of the scale, according to the opinions of the experts who were presented to them, and the relative weight of each field was estimated according to a seven-graded scale, and after analyzing their responses statistically using the Fisher equation) Fisher,1957, p. 2 ,(to calculate the relative weight of each field, it turned out that it varies in the strength of its measurement, then the researchers approximated the value of the relative weight to be an integer, because the number of paragraphs that will measure each field in the scale will be determined in the light of the value of its relative weights, and thus the number of paragraphs of the initial image of the scale became (147) paragraphs covering (13) sub-skills that collectively constitute the three main skills of the first component - knowledge self-awareness, and (14) sub-skills that together constitute the three main skills of the second component - self-regulation of knowledge and the table () shows the distribution of the scale's paragraphs on its main areas As well as the relative weights of these areas

TableNumber of fields, relative weight, and number of paragraphs for each field

number of paragraphs	relative weight	Sub skills	main skills
The first component: self-awareness of knowledge			
8	5.44	A- Awareness of concepts	First - Conceptual knowledge:
8	5.44	NS-? Terminology awareness	

5	3.40	NS-? Symbol Awareness	
6	4.08	d- awareness of the laws	
5	3.40	e- realizing steps	Second - procedural knowledge:
7	4.76	f- Knowledge of models	
5	3.40	g-knowing solutions	
6	4.08	NS-? Knowing the structures	
5	3.40	i- Awareness of conditions	
7	4.76	j- realizing the reasons	Third - contextual knowledge:
4	2.72	K-give justifications	
4	2.72	L - setting standards	
8	5.44	NS-?problem solving	
The second component: the self-regulation of knowledge			
6	4.08	n-define strategies	Fourth - knowledge management:
6	4.08	Q - make plans	
4	2.72	P-building steps	
4	2.72	P-Awareness of relationships	
4	2.72	r-creating conditions	
4	2.72	s-modify style	Fifthly, knowledge assessment:
4	2.72	t-switch strategy	
6	4.08	u-improving context	
3	2.04	c- Make sure of the solution	
3	2.04	w - re-scheme	
5	3.40	G-Modify outputs	Sixth, organizing knowledge:
9	6.12	y-clarify errors	
7	4.76	z-work processors	
4	2.72	G-Organizing thinking	
147	100	Total	

4- Paragraphs for each area: The researchers adopted the weights of the importance of dimensions in determining the number of items on the scale, which were counted according to this method (147) items covering all areas of the scale.

5- Formulating alternatives: In front of each paragraph, five levels were identified that express the degree of using the method (very high, high, medium, few, rare) and the weights of the degrees (1, 2, 3, 4, 5) were determined for each of the alternatives, respectively.

6- Scale instructions: The purpose of preparing instructions for the scale is to clarify the way in which the examinee answers the paragraphs, by which he guarantees obtaining the best response, so when preparing them, it was taken into account that they are simple, understandable and appropriate to the level of understanding of the sample. The appropriate trend that expresses its actual direction and the real purpose of the research was hidden in order to reduce the potential impact of the social desirability factor Social desirability.

7- Checking the validity of the scale paragraphs: The researchers presented the scale in its initial form to a group of experts specialized in the Arabic language to evaluate it linguistically, and the researcher took their observations in this aspect. The scale items were presented to a group of 17 experts in the fields of (methods of teaching the sciences of the Qur'an and Islamic education, methods of teaching geography, methods of teaching the Holy Qur'an and Islamic education, measurement and evaluation, curricula and general teaching methods, methods of teaching Arabic, methods of teaching education Islamic, educational and psychological sciences, psychology, methods of teaching geography, measurement and evaluation), and in the light of the arbitrators'

opinions, (41) paragraphs were deleted, with (25) paragraphs modified by experts, and (106) paragraphs were kept.

8- Tool correction: Correcting the tool means obtaining the total score for the individual, and the total score for the respondent is calculated by summing the scores on all the measurement items. Scale Likert pentagram (Likert Five Scale) ,as it was classified in front of each of the scale items, it reflects their use of it through their response to the scale items, as their responses to the scale items were as in the table(5)Five-point Likert Scale

Answer alternatives to measure the extent to which teachers of forensic sciences in faculties of education practice metacognitive skills

Alternatives				
rare	Few	medium	High	very high
1	2	3	4	5

The total score for each respondent was calculated by the algebraic summation of the scores of his responses on all items of the scale. In theory, the highest score a respondent can get is (530) and the lowest score is (106)

Experimentation with the tool:

This study aimed to identify the clarity of the paragraphs and instructions for individual sample in terms of wording and meaning .The tool was applied to a random sample of (5) male and (5) female teachers from the Iraqi University. The two researchers applied the tool individually in order to be able to answer the questions of the respondents .I explained to them the method of answering and discussed with them the clarity and formulation of the instructions and paragraphs. Through this application, it became clear that the instructions and paragraphs are clear

Psychometric indicators of the tool

1-Honesty:-Validity indicates whether the scale actually measures what it was intended to measure or what we wanted it to measure .It is defined as the degree of the scale's ability to measure what it was designed to measure, and it is also defined as the extent to which the scale meets the specific purposes and uses for which it was designed(Mikhael, 2015: 86)The American Psychological Association has identified APAIn 1975, there were three types of validity: content validity, construct validity, and criterion related validity. AP A,1985: 9 , (and in the current scale there are two indicators: content validity and construct validity.

2- Content authenticity :In their study, the researchers relied on the content validity, as the apparent validity is one of the aspects of content validity. The student studies it) .Kawfeh, 2010: 113)

The validity of the content indicates the extent to which the test content represents the comprehensive behavioral range of the trait to be inferred, as the content must be a good representation of the vocabulary range that was previously determined.Vocabulary scope means: the knowledge, skills, and processes that are examined by the vocabulary of the test .This can be done by analyzing the behavioral content or scope so that the test represents all components of that content or scope well) .Allam, 2000: 190)This form of honesty is used in the achievement tests that are specifically intended to provide the requirements for their validity .However, this does not mean that this form is for achievement tests alone, as tests and other psychological and educational measurement tools must be honest in their content) .Mikhael, 2015: 88)The researchers relied on this type of honesty to verify the validity of the tool by presenting it to a group of arbitrators, whose number was (17) in various specializations, as shown in Appendix (4). Taking into account the most important instructions and directives that they referred to, the scale has been prepared in its final form if the number of paragraphs becomes (106) distributed over (6) main skills that collectively constitute metacognitive skills

3-The validity of the structure or the internal consistency: There are hypothetical indicators that can reveal the validity of the construction, if the degrees of the scale match with it, then this indicates the validity of the construction. Therefore, the researchers extracted indicators of the validity of the hypothetical composition of the current scale by withdrawing (50) forms from the application forms on the basic sample, and the data obtained It is obtained from the responses of the individuals of this sample in calculating the correlation coefficients using the Pearson correlation coefficient using a program SPSS And as follows:

1- Paragraph score and the total score for the domain to which it belongs: The correlation between the score of each item of the scale and the total score for the domain to which it belongs was calculated .The researchers used the Pearson correlation coefficient for the purpose of finding the correlation between the degree of one paragraph and the total degree of the domain to which it belongs. Correlation of a function as it is higher than the tabular value (0.273) at the degree of freedom (49) and at the level of significance (0.05), and that is why it is considered as honest paragraphs of what was designed to be measured .

2- The degree of the field in the domain of the scale:see anastasy Anastasi The correlations of the sub-domains with the total score are essential measures of homogeneity because they help define the domain of behavior to be measured(Anastasi, 1976, p.155)and the correlation coefficients between the sub-domains of the metacognitive skills scale were calculated , and for this the results indicated that the correlation coefficients of

the total degree of the domain with the same domain and other domains ranged between (1-0.68), which are significant correlation coefficients as they are higher than the tabular value (0.273). At a degree of freedom (49) and significance level of (0.05)

3- The total score for the field and the total score for the questionnaire: see Anastasi Anastasi The correlations of the sub-domains with the total score are essential measures of homogeneity because they help define the domain of behavior to be measured) Anastasi, 1976: 155 Therefore, the results indicated that the correlation coefficients between the total score of the field and the total score of the questionnaire ranged between (0.89-1), which are significant correlation coefficients as they are higher than the tabular value (0.273) at the degree of freedom (49) and at the level of significance (0.05), as shown in the table.()

Table Correlation coefficients between the total score of the domain and the total score of the scale using the Pearson correlation coefficient

correlation coefficient	Sub components	main ingredients
0.96	First, the conceptual knowledge	The first component: self-awareness of knowledge
0.97	Second, procedural knowledge	
0.91	Third, contextual knowledge	The second component: the self-regulation of knowledge:
0.89	Fourth, knowledge management	
0.93	Fifthly, the assessment of knowledge	
0.93	Sixth, organizing knowledge	
1	Totalmarks	

Second - the stability of the tool

Stability is defined as the stability of the results when the test is re-applied to individuals and the preservation of the true variance of the test (The Tiger, 2008: 77) The researchers adopted the data of the hypothetical formation validity sample, which consisted of (50) male and female teachers, to ensure the stability of the scale items by adopting two methods:

Half-segmentation: which means splitting the scale after its application into two halves by considering the even questions as a measure and the odd questions as another measure and extracting the stability and correlation coefficient between the two scales (The Tiger, 2008: 84)

table The value of the stability coefficient of a scale by the hash-half method

Metacognition skills

Spearman Brown	Pearson correlation coefficient	Number of paragraphs for each part
0.97	0.94	53

By observing the table (), it becomes clear to us that the stability coefficient of the scale as a whole is (0.97), which are acceptable stability coefficients for the purposes of research and research, as it fell within the appropriate range that Likert and his colleagues assumed, where Likert and his colleagues determined the appropriate range for the acceptable stability coefficient of the trend scale is the range that ranges between (0.62 - 0.93) (Abd al-Rahman, 1992, p. 207), which indicates the accuracy of the measurement.

The method of analysis of variance using the Facronbach coefficient equation

The stability extracted in this way expresses the extent to which the items in the scale measure the same thing, and if the items actually measure the same trait, they must be correlated with each other. Costa & McCrae, 1992b, p (44) the stability was calculated in this way, and its rates ranged between (0.93-0.86), and the table () shows that.

Table Reliability coefficients calculated using the analysis of variance method for the resolution domains and the resolution as a whole

Cronbach's alpha coefficient	number of paragraphs	Sub components	main ingredients
0.92	23	First, the conceptual knowledge	The first component: self-awareness of knowledge
0.88	18	Second, procedural knowledge	
0.91	20	Third, contextual knowledge	

0.89	18	Fourth, knowledge management	The second component: the self-regulation of knowledge:
0.87	13	Fifthly, the assessment of knowledge	
0.86	14	Sixth, organizing knowledge	
0.93	106	Total marks	

By observing the table (), it turns out that the Facronbach stability coefficient for conceptual knowledge is (0.92), for procedural knowledge it is (0.88), and for contextual knowledge is (0.91), and the Facronbach reliability coefficient for knowledge management is (0.89), and for knowledge evaluation is (0.87), and that The Facronbach reliability coefficient for organizing knowledge is (0.86)It was found that the Facronbach stability coefficient for the scale as a whole is (0.93), which are stability coefficients Accepted for research and research purposes as it was judged by using the absolute criterion by squaring the calculated stability coefficient (Al-Bayati and Athanasius, 1977: 194)

Means statistic:- The researchers used the statistical bag for social sciences) spssFor the purpose of processing statistical data, and extracting results :

1. The single-sample chi-square test (χ^2) was used to find out the significance of the difference between the number of experts who agreed on the tool areas and those who did not, and between the number of experts who agreed on the tool items and those who did not.
2. (Ahmed 1989 p. 284).
3. Pearson's correlation coefficient: People's correlation coefficient: to know the relationship between the score of each paragraph and the total score of the scale and the relationship between the domain score and the total score of the scale and the score of the domain with a domain.
4. (Ferrickson: 1991, 145)
5. Spearman-Brown equation in calculating stability by split method.
6. (Al-Rawi 2000: 98).
7. Cronbach's alpha equation (Cronbach's alpha formula) was used to calculate the stability by the internal consistency method.
8. (Abd al-Rahman, 1998: 172).
9. Weighted average
10. (Medical, 2008: 50)
11. Paragraph Weight Ratio
12. (Adass, 1978: 133)
13. T-test for two independent samples of unequal size to find differences between members of the sample in terms of gender and educational qualifications.
14. (Al-Bayati and Athanasius, 1977: 274)
15. One-way analysis of variance to find the differences between the sample members in terms of length of service.

The fourth chapter presents the results, recommendations and suggestions

The goal of the research has been achieved in building a scale for metacognitive skills for the curricula of the departments of Quranic sciences and Islamic education in Iraqi universities, and we can provide a general description of the scale that was built as follows:

1. In its final form, the scale consists of (106) items distributed over (6) main skills that collectively constitute metacognitive skills .
2. Paragraphs (5) were given alternatives to the answer, which are (very high, high, medium, few, rare) and the weights of the degrees (1,2,3,4,5) were determined for each of the alternatives, respectively, and thus the highest score for the scale (530) and the lowest score (106)
3. The validity of the scale was verified, as two indicators were available:

Content authenticity

This type of honesty was adopted to verify the validity of the scale by presenting it to a group of arbitrators, numbering (17) in various specializations, and based on the opinion of the majority in the validity of the scale to measure the goal for which it was set. The scale has been prepared in its final form if the number of paragraphs becomes (106) distributed over (6) main skills that collectively constitute metacognitive skills .

The validity of the construction or internal consistency

Indicators of the validity of the default configuration for the current scale were extracted, which are:

1. The degree of the paragraph and the total degree of the field to which it belongs, the degree of the field in the domain of the scale, the total degree of the field and the total degree of the questionnaire.
2. The stability of the scale was verified in two ways:
3. Half-segmentation method: the scale stability rates ranged between (0.62 - 0.93)
4. The method of analysis of variance using the Facronbach equation: the scale stability rates ranged between (0.93-0.86)

Suggestions

The researchers suggest conducting the following studies as complementary studies to the current research:

1. Measuring the metacognitive skills of the curricula of the departments of Quranic sciences and Islamic education in the colleges of education in Iraqi universities.
2. Measuring the metacognitive skills of the curricula of the departments of Quranic sciences and Islamic education in Iraqi universities in light of their relationship to some demographic variables.
3. Building a proposed training program to train forensic science teachers to use meta-knowledge skills in teaching forensic sciences.

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